

D5.2 DECO Strategy

Prepared by: KASKAS

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

DECO	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach
Dx.x	Deliverable number
PMG	Project Management Group
PC	Project Coordinator
ICEBERG	Innovative Community Engagement for Building Effective Resilience and Arctic-Ocean Pollution-Control Governance in the context of Climate Change

1 Introduction

Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach (DECO) activities are crucial to increase the societal impact of the project. This DECO strategy describes how project progress will be communicated and its results disseminated and made available for exploitation. Its goal is to ensure effective planning, management and implementation of DECO activities.

Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach (DECO) activities are crucial to increase the societal impact of the project. This DECO strategy describes how project progress will be communicated and its results disseminated and made available for exploitation. Its goal is to ensure effective planning, management and implementation of DECO activities.

- **Dissemination** = Dissemination means the ways to transfer the knowledge and results of the project for others to use them.
- **Exploitation** = Exploitation means the ways to utilise the project's results through scientific, economic, political or societal exploitation routes. The aim is to turn the results into concrete values and impact to the society.
- **Communication** = Communication means the ways to raise awareness, interest and understanding of the project and its benefits.
- **Outreach** = Outreach highlights reaching out and creating common understanding especially with the local communities affected by the project's topics and activities.

Production of the strategy was led by KASKAS in close collaboration with the consortium. A survey to the consortium was conducted in January 2024, marking the beginning of the strategy process. The process continued with two co-creation workshops with DECO Board members, both held in February 2024, where different sections of the strategy were further developed.

The strategy and content plan will be regularly assessed and updated in co-creation sessions with the internal DECO Board (table 1) and external Advisory Board (see D6.1 Quality Assurance Plan).

2 Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach objectives

The **communication and outreach objectives** of the project are:

- enhancing project visibility and engagement by actively communicating, raising awareness and interest of its objectives, processes, activities and outcomes to the general public and the project's defined stakeholders and target audiences. This entails also engaging with communities, stakeholders and target audiences at various stages of the project's development. By adopting this process-oriented approach, the project fosters understanding and cultivates support from a broad spectrum of interested actors, maximising its potential for success
- increasing understanding, dialogue and exchange of information between the project and its stakeholders
- ensuring a practical co-design approach for inclusive communication activities together with the project partners, rights holders and stakeholders.

The **dissemination and exploitation objectives** of the project are:

- sharing and promoting the project's results and achievements by engaging and involving relevant stakeholders
- creating synergies and networks with other EU projects and initiatives
- ensuring broad and long-term exploitation of the results within the affected communities and stakeholders through interaction to understand and answer to their needs.

3 DECO principles and roles

3.1 Principles for DECO

The project follows a set of DECO principles that guide the planning and implementation of the DECO activities. These principles have been selected and prioritised together with the consortium.

The key principles for DECO in the project are:

- **Clarity and Relevance:** We ensure our messages are clear, understandable and relevant to the audience we are communicating to.
- **Honesty and Transparency:** We are open and truthful in our communications.
- **Cultural Sensitivity:** We are aware of and respect cultural differences in communication styles.
- **Respect and empathy:** We show respect for others' opinions, even when they differ from our own. We understand and acknowledge our audience's perspectives and feelings.

3.2 DECO roles

The planning and implementation of DECO activities is led by **KASKAS** (WP5). KASKAS manages and updates ICEBERG's own external communication channels and provides supporting materials and guidelines for the project partners to conduct DECO activities in their own channels and networks. KASKAS collaborates with all the consortium partners in the content creation for the project.

The DECO activities are planned and executed in close collaboration with other project partners. To ensure that all different viewpoints from the consortium are considered, a **DECO Board** consisting of representatives of each work package and each case study site was formed at the beginning of the project (table 1). The board meets multiple times a year to co-create and consult DECO activities in the project. In addition to the DECO Board, KASKAS informs and collects insights and contributions from the consortium through other internal channels and meetings continuously throughout the project.

Table 1. The Composition of the DECO Board

WP/Case Study	Names of Representatives/Affiliation	Email
WP1	Markus Schartau / GEOMAR	mschartau@geomar.de
WP2	Apostolos Papakonstantinou / SCI Gaud Dervilly / ONIRIS (Substitute)	apapak@scidrones.com gaud.dervilly@inrae.fr
WP3	Adam Stepien / ULAP Jóse Luiz Moutinho / AIRCentre (Substitute) Valerie de Liedekerke / AIRCentre (Substitute)	adam.stepien@ulapland.fi jose.moutinho@aircentre.org valerie.deliedekerke@aircentre.org
WP4	Anne Chahine / GFZ (RIFS) Christine Liang / UFZ (Substitute)	anne.chahine@rifs-potsdam.de christine.liang@ufz.de
WP5	Paavo Antikainen / KASKAS KASKAS Team (Substitute)	paavo.antikainen@kaskas.fi iceberg-wp5@lists.oulu.fi

WP/Case Study	Names of Representatives/Affiliation	Email
WP6	Élise Lépy / UOULU	elise.lepy@oulu.fi
Svalbard	Beatrice Rosso / CNR	beatrice.rosso@isp.cnr.it
Greenland (Kalaallit Nunaat)	Ilona Mettiäinen / ULAP	ilona.mettiainen@ulapland.fi
Iceland	Joan Nymand Larsen / SAI	jnl@unak.is
Scientific Coordinator	Thora Herrmann / UOULU	thora.herrmann@oulu.fi

KASKAS also collaborates and consults ICEBERG’s **sibling Horizon Europe projects** (ILLUQ and ArcSolution) and **other relevant networks** (such as the EU Polar Cluster and EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters) in the DECO activities. Connections to these projects and networks are established within the first six months of the project. Close collaboration with these actors is important to avoid stakeholder fatigue and to maximise the impact of ICEBERG’s DECO activities.

In addition to the consortium and relevant networks, some DECO activities are also developed in closer **interaction with other stakeholders and target audiences**, especially activities that are targeted to Indigenous rights holders, local communities and policy-makers.

4 Project identity

This section deals with ICEBERG's project identity, including tone of voice, key messages, languages and visual identity. A more comprehensive and detailed description and instructions for applying the visual identity can be found in D5.1 and will be detailed in ICEBERG's brand book (coming soon).

4.1 Tone of Voice

A tone of voice in communications refers to the mood or attitude conveyed in a piece of writing, speech or post. It is a description of what ICEBERG sounds like to the broad public audiences and in what way are the ICEBERG's messages conveyed. The tone of voice does not apply to scientific publications, policy briefs or other material produced for specific expert audiences.

ICEBERG's tone of voice consists of four elements:

- **Understandable**

ICEBERG aims to ensure that project's communication is accessible and understandable to non-specialist audiences i.e. avoids abbreviations, project jargon, difficult scientific terms and inaccurate language.

- **Humane**

The project communicates in an approachable and human way. The research is told through the voices and experiences of the people involved. We recognize our identity not only as a faceless research entity, but as a collective of individuals representing diverse regions and communities. By adopting a self-reflexive stance, we move from passive expression and representation to active engagement, presenting ourselves as integral parts of the narrative. Adopting such a way of communicating fosters authenticity, empathy and connection, enabling us to effectively communicate the essence of our project's mission and impacts.

- **Hopeful**

All communication of the project conveys a solution-oriented approach to solving difficult challenges and enabling a better future. In doing this, ICEBERG's communications is open, truthful and avoids cutting corners and coming across as falsely positive.

- **Trustworthy**

The information ICEBERG shares is based on collaborative knowledge production and research.

4.2 Key messages

Key messages form the foundation of the communication of the ICEBERG project. They help the project partners to communicate the project's purpose, activities and goals in a consistent way throughout different communication channels and organisations.

However, key messages can be modified to serve the specific needs and interests of different target groups as well as to take into account the different stages of the project.

In the beginning of the project, the key messages will focus on the project's purpose, activities and goals. In the later stages of the project, the key messages will focus more on the project's results.

The ICEBERG's key message is:

ICEBERG studies ocean and coastal pollution and creates governance and resilience strategies with European Arctic communities.

Supporting messages deepen and contextualise the core message and answer the questions why, how and what. The ICEBERG's supporting messages are:

Climate change and pollution such as plastics, ship emissions and wastewater, are threatening our health and ecosystems in the Arctic.

For the EU to reach its Zero Pollution Ambition, we need a deeper understanding of the complex interplay of pollution and climate change as well as its impacts on ecosystems and communities in the Arctic.

ICEBERG studies sources, types, distribution of pollution and its impacts on the ecosystems and communities in Kalaallit Nunaat (Greenland), Iceland and Svalbard.

Together with Indigenous and local communities, we co-develop pollution monitoring, mitigation and adaptation strategies using a One Health approach and policy recommendations for multilevel pollution-control governance.

ICEBERG merges natural and social sciences with Indigenous and local knowledge. The project uses an ethical multi-actor and gender-sensitive approach to assess the impacts, risks and vulnerabilities of local communities.

Through innovative community engagement, we strive to increase community and ecosystem resilience to pollution and climate change in the Arctic.

4.3 Languages

English is the main communication language of the project ICEBERG. English is the main language used in the project's own communication channels and materials (e.g. website, social media channels and newsletters).

Other languages are used in the project's communication and interaction with local, regional and national stakeholders within the consortium partner countries. Special attention is paid to communication in the languages of local communities (Greenlandic and Icelandic). Communication materials are translated into local languages when needed.

4.4 Visual identity

The project's visual identity is minimalistic, moderate and heartfelt. It combines social and natural sciences and humanities clearly and simply. The logo is simple and minimalistic, but the image style brings the human

feeling alive. A more comprehensive and detailed description and instructions for applying the visual identity can be found in D5.1 and will be detailed in ICEBERG's brand book (coming soon).

5 Target groups, stakeholders and rights holders

This section lists ICEBERG's key target groups, stakeholders and rights holders. A more comprehensive and detailed list of stakeholders participating in the research activities is developed by WP4 and will be also used for the DECO activities.

5.1 DECO target groups, stakeholders and rights holders

ICEBERG has seven key target groups, stakeholders and rights holders which are listed below. These groups were defined in collaboration with DECO Board members during one of the workshops. A more comprehensive and detailed description of each key target group, stakeholders and rights holders and examples of channels which can be used to reach them is in Table 2 below.

ICEBERG'S KEY TARGET GROUPS, STAKEHOLDERS AND RIGHTS HOLDERS:

- international environmental officials, policy makers and non-governmental organisations
- local, regional and national policy makers in the Arctic
- Indigenous and local communities
- private sector
- scientific community
- media and journalists
- general public

Table 2. List of target groups, stakeholders and rights holders and examples of channels to reach them

Target Group, Stakeholder and Rights Holder name	Target Group, Stakeholder and Rights Holder description	Examples of channels to reach them
International Environmental Officials, Policy Makers and NGOs	Officials in the EU and Arctic region responsible for environmental legislation and policy. Organisations like the Arctic Council and its working groups crucial in global Arctic environmental initiatives.	Personal relationships and direct outreach, newspapers, policy forums, conferences and other events, including Arctic Dialog organised by the German Arctic Office.
Local, Regional and National Policy Makers in the Arctic	Authorities managing local environmental issues and policies in the Arctic.	Networks such as NGOs, other advocacy groups and environmental organisations, events and direct outreach.
Indigenous and Local Communities	Representatives and leaders of Indigenous and local groups in the Arctic, especially in Iceland and Greenland (Kalaallit Nunaat), who are	Facebook, local media, local contact persons, organisations and local events.

Target Group, Stakeholder and Rights Holder name	Target Group, Stakeholder and Rights Holder description	Examples of channels to reach them
	directly affected by the region's environmental health.	
Private Sector	Fisheries sector, polluting industries, waste management companies, tourist agencies and shipping companies, etc. operating in the area.	Arctic Circle Assembly and other Arctic conferences with businesses involved, direct contacts, Air Greenland in-flight magazine, national (and regional) tourism organisation networks and business associations.
Scientific Community	Researchers and research communities studying similar topics and/or operating in the same area (including sibling projects and EU Polar Cluster).	Conferences, personal relationships and scientific journals.
Media and Journalists	Media professionals disseminating information and raising public awareness.	Press conferences and press releases, social media and direct outreach to journalists.
General Public	Those interested in the Arctic and/or interested in environmental issues more generally (e.g. pollution, climate change)	Via media, social media channels and project website.

6 Channels and means

Project ICEBERG uses various channels and tools in its dissemination, exploitation, communication and outreach activities. Different channels and means are used to ensure that ICEBERG's communication activities reach all key target groups, stakeholders and rights holders.

6.1 Website

The project website is published at the beginning of the project in M3. Before the final project website is published, a temporary one-pager has been used to provide the basic information about the project, from M2 onwards.

The project website is targeted at all the target groups, stakeholders and rights holders who are interested in ICEBERG and want to find out more about the project. The website offers information on the project's:

- goals, timeline, and outputs
- research questions and topics
- partners
- case studies
- contact information and
- funding

On the website, the project will publish and link:

- frameworks, models and data created in the project
- latest scientific articles, policy briefs, deliverables, media coverage, and presentations, which are interesting to target groups, stakeholders and rights holders
- blog posts (also including news and events)
- links to the project's social media channels and a newsletter subscription form

The website URL is <https://arcticeberg.eu>. The website is maintained and updated by KASKAS.

6.2 Social media

ICEBERG is developing four social media channels: X (twitter), Facebook, LinkedIn and YouTube. KASKAS is responsible for opening these social media channels within the first six months of the project. All channels are updated and maintained by KASKAS.

New social media channels can be opened during the project if they meet the strategic need. Likewise, a channel can be closed if it does not serve the strategy and reach key target groups, stakeholders and rights holders. New channels have to be discussed within the DECO Board.

Decisions to open new channels are based on potential to reach target demographics and achieve strategic goals, while considerations for closing channels are focused on underperformance, resource inefficiency or misalignment with project values.

X (Twitter)

The project's X communication will be executed via its own X profile. An X profile will be created in M4–5. Project partners and individual project members are also encouraged to use their own X profiles to communicate with the project's target groups and stakeholders and to share content about ICEBERG.

Communication in X will be targeted and connections created especially focused toward the scientific community, environmental officials and policymakers on different levels and journalists.

X will be used to share knowledge on the project's development, recent news, events and results of the project. The project's X profile is updated by KASKAS.

Facebook

ICEBERG has its own Facebook page, "Arctic ICEBERG", which is mainly used to reach Indigenous and local communities and also the general public. Link to the Facebook page: <https://www.facebook.com/arcticeberg/>

LinkedIn

ICEBERG will have its own LinkedIn page. The LinkedIn channel of the project will be used to reach international, regional and local expert audiences, including the scientific community, International Environmental Officials, Policy Makers and NGOs, Local, Regional and National Policy Makers in the Arctic as well as Private sector stakeholders. The LinkedIn channel will be opened in M5.

YouTube

A YouTube channel will be created for the project where all the videos produced in the project can be uploaded. The videos will be produced mainly by KASKAS or by the case study participants. The videos will be shared mainly through linking or embedding in other communication channels.

The project's YouTube channel is updated by KASKAS.

6.3 Newsletter

The project will have an e-newsletter targeted to all target and stakeholder groups. It will be sent approximately twice a year and includes the latest blog posts, event invitations, project news and materials. Every case study, workshop and seminar participant is encouraged to subscribe to ICEBERG's newsletter and the newsletter will be also promoted through ICEBERG's social media channels and website. The project uses Mailchimp newsletter platform and newsletters are produced and sent by KASKAS. KASKAS will consult the DECO Board before sending the newsletters.

6.4 Research publications

Open access scientific publications are produced to transfer knowledge and make the project results available for exploitation within the academic community. The publications are sent to open-access academic journals and linked to the project website.

6.5 Policy briefs

ICEBERG will produce policy briefs and reports towards the end of the project. The briefs will be distributed to decision-makers through the appropriate channels e.g. social media channels, the newsletter and in different events and workshops. WP3 is responsible for producing and distributing the policy briefs. KASKAS will help WP3 with the policy briefs from the production to distribution.

6.6 Events

Events

ICEBERG will be present in relevant events organised by the project's stakeholders and in events organised in the field of ICEBERG's research. ICEBERG will participate in policy-focused events (Arctic- as well as pollution- or marine environment- focused) and organising policy-briefings (e.g. EU institutions and, if possible, policy-makers in Greenland and Iceland). Case studies will be present in local events that will help to promote the project and engage case study participants. The events can be organised either as physical or virtual events. Participation as a project in EU level events will be decided by WP6.

Academic conferences

The project partners and members participate in multiple conferences, seminars and research days during the project. The goal is to promote the project and disseminate the project results to the scientific community. Conferences also offer opportunities to collaborate with other researchers and projects.

6.7 Media relations

Press releases

The project publishes press releases when important information is produced in the project. Press releases are produced by KASKAS together with the project partners. The DECO Board approves the press releases and decides on the distribution. The releases include information about the project results and major events. Releases are distributed to media outlets and journalists in the case study countries and to international media.

Media pitches

In addition to press releases, all project partners can contact journalists and media outlets and pitch story ideas. A media pitch is an attempt to get a journalist or editor interested in your news so that they decide to cover it, resulting in media coverage. KASKAS helps other partners to contact journalists and formulate the pitches.

6.8 Promotional materials

Brochures

ICEBERG produces brochures that are distributed to the case study participants, decision-makers and local and Indigenous communities in workshops, seminars and other events. The first ICEBERG brochure will be produced in year 1. Its function is to offer general information on the project and its goals.

Videos

Videos are used to raise awareness of the project, its goals and findings. Videos are targeted to all target groups, stakeholders and rights holders and distributed through ICEBERG's social media channels and in events.

First, a short promotional video will be produced by the project in year 1. The video is used to promote the project for ICEBERG's key target groups, stakeholders and rights holders. In the final project year, a behind-the-scenes video documenting the project's journey will be produced.

The project also distributes and promotes videos and other visual materials produced as part of the citizen science activities by the case study participants.

Roll-ups

Roll-ups are used in academic and non-academic events. They are present in external project workshops and seminars that take place face-to-face. ICEBERG roll-up will be designed in year 1.

Other promotional materials

Other promotional materials (for example t-shirts or hoodies) may be produced if deemed necessary for events to promote the project to the general audience and local and Indigenous communities. The production of such physical promotional materials will always be seriously considered from the environmental point of view to minimise the use of resources and to avoid generating waste. Other promotional materials may also include digital visual materials, such as banners.

6.9 Collaboration and interaction

Collaboration with other projects, networks, associations and initiatives

ICEBERG will host various actions/activities (thematic meetings, inviting external key actors and members of other relevant projects to GA meetings and webinars) to encourage fruitful exchange, create spaces and opportunities to share and transfer the knowledge, lessons, experiences, outcomes and tools developed by the project with other projects.

Local communication activities with case study participants

Case study participants can participate in communication activities in different ways e.g., rural communicators/storytellers, local exhibitions in Museums in Narsaq, Akureyri, photo contest, participatory Indigenous short film production and rural radio/podcast. These activities will be decided later by case study participants.

Citizen participation platform

To support the exploitation and dissemination of the project results in and across Indigenous and local communities, an interactive citizen participation platform will provide space for knowledge co-creation. In addition to in-person community-to-community exchanges, the platform will also become a space for community-based environmental monitoring and mapping experience sharing and networking.

An open-source and free interactive mapping platform, such as *uMap* (which uses OpenStreetMap layers and can be embed in a website) or *Mapbox* (also OpenStreetMap-based) will be used. Training sessions on interactive online mapping with local curators in Kalaallit Nunaat and in Iceland will be organised.

The interactive map will provide data visualisation of the submitted local observations, photos and videos. The mapping platform will display different regions of the study sites and each geotagged point on the map would represent one observation, with the option to click the point and further expand the reported data along with the uploaded photo or video or audiofile (for stories linked to places). The webform could either be linked to the map, with submitted data automatically loaded onto the map (after curator approval), or curators could be tasked with manually inputting the information from the webform into the map after evaluating the data.

In both study sites efforts will be made to link the interactive online mapping platform with locally operating community-based environmental monitoring initiatives, such as PISUNA in Kalaallit Nunaat (Greenland), in order to ensure that the continuity and sustainability of environmental monitoring activities are maintained beyond the duration of our project, facilitating ongoing local data collection, analysis, and community engagement to enhance informed decision-making and long-term pollution mitigation goals.

6.10 Project partners' channels

In addition to ICEBERG's official communication channels and tools, all consortium partners use their organisations' channels, networks and partnerships to advance the communication and dissemination goals of the project. This is done through sharing ICEBERG's content and communicating about ICEBERG in their channels, events and workshops and interacting directly with their networks and partners.

6.11 Internal communication

Channels of internal communication are organised by WP6 (see D6.1 Quality Assurance Plan).

7 Preliminary plan for year 1

The DECO activities during the first year focus strongly on establishing connections to the stakeholders and promoting the project. These activities will build the basis for successful collaboration with the stakeholders throughout the project as well as effective dissemination and exploitation of the results.

The goals for DECO activities for the first project year are to:

- promote the project to the general audience and all the relevant stakeholders
- build trusts especially with Indigenous and local communities in the project's case study areas
- networking with sibling projects and other relevant networks to maximise the project's impact and avoid creating stakeholder fatigue.

The first period of fieldwork will take place during the first project year. Therefore, a strong emphasis will be put on introducing the project to the local stakeholders and promoting the opportunities to participate in the citizen science activities.

From a governance point of view, there are a few relevant events to which the project can contribute by participating in the discussion. For example, in M4, the 4th session of the Intergovernmental Negotiating Committee to develop an international legally binding instrument on plastic pollution, including the marine environment (INC-4), will be held from 23 to 29 April 2024 at the Shaw Center in Ottawa, Canada. In the beginning of the project year, new EU level restrictions on microplastics have also been implemented which can provide a relevant discussion for ICEBERG participation.

Table 3. Preliminary plan for the first year's DECO activities

	M1-M3 Jan – March	M4-M6 Apr – Jun	M7-M9 Jul – Sept	M10-M12 Oct – Dec
Infrastructure and Collaboration	Establishing DECO Board M1 DECO Strategy (including two co-creation workshops with DECO Board) by M3 Project identity by M3	Establishing and promoting the citizen participation platform (inc. virtual chat room for the local communities) Recruiting "curators" that can speak the local language and help to translate the website and platforms for citizens to interact Establishing connections with sibling project and other networks	Communication training for the partners M9 Meetings with sibling projects and planning joint activities towards policy-makers	
Materials for the consortium	Preliminary PPT template for the kick off	PPT and social media templates		

	M1-M3 Jan – March	M4-M6 Apr – Jun	M7-M9 Jul – Sept	M10-M12 Oct – Dec
		Materials for fieldwork: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • project info ppt • brochure • project video • merchandise (T-shirt design, stickers, etc.) 		
Website and social media	Facebook page and first posts M1 One pager website M1 Website by M3	Establishing other social media channels News article of ICEBERG project M4 Communication related to the Plastic Treaty / EU Microplastics regulations (WP3) Content concepts for blog and social media Promoting the citizen participation platform	Content from fieldwork Promoting the citizen participation platform Promoting ICEBERG project Approx. 1 blog post per month	Approx. 1 blog post per month Promoting ICEBERG project
Newsletter		Gathering the stakeholder list M4 Promoting the newsletter to stakeholders	First newsletter	
Media comms		Press release of the project	Local media communication	
Events		EU Arctic Forum and the Indigenous Peoples' Dialogue on 14 and 15 May 2024 in Brussels		
Key ICEBERG activities and relevant societal events for the project		WP1 fieldwork in Svalbard starts in M4 and will continue until M8. The 4th session of UN Plastic Treaty (INC-4) 23- 29 April 2024		

	M1-M3 Jan – March	M4-M6 Apr – Jun	M7-M9 Jul – Sept	M10-M12 Oct – Dec
		New EU microplastics regulations agreed by the Council and the Parliament		

8 Preliminary dissemination and exploitation plan

The ICEBERG project has a twofold aim:

- to produce a deeper understanding of pollution and its impacts on ecosystems and communities in the Arctic in combination with climate-induced stressors
- to create strategies for enhancing community-led resilience and adaptation as well as pollution-control governance and policy recommendations.

In addition, the project aims to develop new knowledge and tools for ethical and inclusive citizen science practices.

The aim of the dissemination activities in the ICEBERG project is to ensure that the results reach the potential users and cater to their needs. As the project has a strong emphasis on community engagement with Indigenous and local communities and the results concern their health and livelihoods, this stakeholder group is taken into a special consideration in the dissemination activities to ensure that they can comment on the results and are able to exploit them.

See Annex 1 for description of the full list of Expected Results.

Table 4. The preliminary dissemination and exploitation plan for the project's results. The plan will be updated during the project.

Description of the Exploitable Results	Main uses	Main users	Dissemination products and activities	Estimated schedule for the first results
<p>Advanced knowledge on:</p> <p>R1-3: release of frozen-locked pollutants from snow, ice & permafrost</p> <p>R4-7: quantitative, qualitative & distributional data of pollution, especially plastic pollution in Arctic littoral zones</p> <p>R8-10: role of microplastics, associated antibiotic resistant bacteria & antibiotic resistance genes and other</p>	<p><i>Preliminary results</i> will be used in community engagement with local communities to develop policy recommendations and strategies for local communities</p> <p><i>The final results</i> will be exploited in further research and education</p>	<p>Indigenous and Local Communities</p> <p>Private sector operating in the Arctic (e.g. tourist companies that maintain cruise ships)</p> <p>International Environmental Bodies (e.g. PAME, Protection of the Arctic Marine Environment)</p> <p>Scientific community</p>	<p>Citizen participation platform (Iceland & Greenland)</p> <p>Communication activities especially in Svalbard for locals & tourists (for example, Museums)</p> <p>Illustrations</p> <p>Brief scientific reports</p> <p>Newsletters</p> <p>Scientific publications</p> <p>Events and conferences</p> <p>Website</p>	<p>Preliminary results in M16</p> <p>Final results in M30-34</p>

Description of the Exploitable Results	Main uses	Main users	Dissemination products and activities	Estimated schedule for the first results
contaminants, on ecosystem & human health R11-13: sensitivity of lower trophic food web to pollutants in combination with climate-induced stressors				
R12-R15: Sanitary quality of food chain and human health impacts of micro and nano plastic and other contaminants R16: Community observations of changes, impacts and risks on health and well-being, identity, culture and economy R17: Community scenarios of change and adaptation and mitigation strategies to increase community and ecosystem resilience. R18: Community-based environmental monitoring programme	Local pollution monitoring Local mitigation to the effects of pollution and climate change <i>Results</i> R12-16 will be used with local communities to develop policy recommendations and strategies for local communities/municipalities Policy action at regional level (marine protection areas, etc.) Pan-European Arctic Cit Sci monitoring platform	Indigenous and Local Communities Local, Regional and National Governments in the Arctic (e.g. public health sector) International Environmental Bodies (e.g. PAME, Protection of the Arctic Environment, Arctic Council and Arctic Council working groups, i.e. Sustainable development working group) Scientific community	Citizen participation platform Local communication activities, e.g., social media, art-based outputs, media, newsletter and events Participation in communication activities e.g., rural communicators/storytellers, local exhibitions in Museums in Narsaq, Akureyri, photo contest, participatory Indigenous short film production and rural radio/podcast 4 reports: - on analysis of community observations of changes, impacts, risks and vulnerabilities and resulting strategies - on food chain contamination - on nano-plastics and other contaminants (PFAS) - on climate related observations and forecasts Briefs targeted to private and public sector (based on scenario report)	

Description of the Exploitable Results	Main uses	Main users	Dissemination products and activities	Estimated schedule for the first results
			Scientific publications Website	
R19: Mapping of current governance frameworks R20-21, R23: Recommendations for - policymakers at different levels on pollution governance, including international actions specifically gender-related actions. - research and assessment focus for the AC and European science funders - local communities in the Arctic on the regulatory and policy aspects of local pollution strategies.	Further research and assessment Policy Local action Research policy and pan-Arctic assessment activities	Scientific community European policy-makers (EC, DG ENV, ECHA, MSs ministries of environment) Science funders (national, private, European) and AC working groups Local stakeholders, community leaders municipal and regional civil-servants	2 reports - recommendations for policy-makers - recommendations for local communities 2 policy briefs - international actions (for EU and MSs policymakers and ECHA) - science funders and AC working groups A brief aimed at women's organisations Summaries and infographics Policy briefings and webinars Collaboration in activities with relevant networks (e.g. AMAP) Website	R19: M15 R20-21, R23: M30 (policymakers and research funding) R21, R23: M32 (local communities)
R22: Advanced understanding of the gendered impact of pollution in the Arctic R24-25: Ethics evaluation framework for co-creative research Guidelines for citizen science	Tools and reference points for internal and external project use on issues related to ethics, gender and citizen science during the project and beyond Evaluation tools for conduct of the consortium Continued local monitoring plan by citizens Long-term monitoring of shoreline and macrolitter change	Consortium partners Scientific community Indigenous and Local Communities Local, Regional and National Governments in the Arctic	Code of conduct DEI shared internally with the consortium Citizen science and co-design framework White paper and Toolbox for Gender dimensions Scientific articles Events and conferences	M6: DEI Code of Conduct M24: Co-creation Framework M30: Gender White Paper and Toolbox

Description of the Exploitable Results	Main uses	Main users	Dissemination products and activities	Estimated schedule for the first results
DEI Code of Conduct for the consortium			Collaboration with local and scientific networks and projects (EU Polar Cluster, Arctic Hub, sibling projects, etc.) Website	

9 Indicators

The success of the DECO activities will be assessed by indicators below. These indicators are updated if necessary.

Table 5. Indicators

Channels and means	Description	Measures of success
Project website	See section 6.1	+ 1000 visits per month (by the end of the project)
Newsletter	See section 6.3	300 subscribers to the newsletter
Social media accounts	See section 6.2	500 followers by project end
Audio-visual material	1 video explaining key project topics and selected results + 1 video storytelling collecting local audio-visual material from case study site	+5000 views
Press releases	To accompany relevant achievements	5 press releases
Local communication activities with case study participants	E.g., rural communicators/storytellers, local exhibitions in Museums in Narsaq, Akureyri, photo contest, participatory Indigenous short film production, rural radio/podcast, blogs, newsletter	Min. 2 activities per case study site + audio-visual material for the storytelling video
Interactive platform for citizen participation	Enhance two-way interaction and engagement between communities and researchers participating in the project	+5000 citizens uploading items
Participating in international and local conferences and organisation of dedicated sessions at conferences	E.g. ASSW; ICASS	min. 6 conferences/public events, at least 2 sessions organised
Publications in scientific journals	Relevant scientific/research journals	min. 8 publications
Joint activities with relevant projects and initiatives on methods, and findings	E.g. EUPolarNet2, ArcticPASSION, ArcticHUBs	min. 3 projects engaged
Community-to-community actions	Webinars, knowledge exchange meetings, etc.	min. 3 actions
Final conference in Brussels to present the outcomes of the project		80 participants

10 Annex 1. *Expected Results (Rs) of the ICEBERG project*

Table 6. Expected Results (Rs) of the ICEBERG project

<p>SO1: Deepen the understanding of the impact of changes in the cryosphere (snow, ice and permafrost) on the release of frozen-locked pollutants into the coastal and open ocean environments (natural/local/regional sources). SO1 will address the Expected Outcomes (EO) EO1 "Advanced scientific understanding of the impacts of pollution [...]".</p>	
<p>Expected Results (Rs)</p> <p>R1. Define the source-to-sink transport of pollutants in rapidly changing environments: a novel mechanistic understanding about the behaviour of organic/inorganic pollutants released from the melting cryosphere and depositing in the Arctic Ocean.</p> <p>R2. Quantitative estimation of the current geochemical background in an unglaciated and uninhabited area of Spitsbergen, with the focus on heavy metals.</p> <p>R3. Ranking pollutants according to their abundance in different matrices (sediments, biota, soils, freshwater and water samples).</p>	<p>KPIs</p> <p>1. Quantification of standing stocks of at least 5 different types of diverse pollutants in 3 case study sites in land/ocean samples.</p> <p>2. Chemical analysis of at least 200 seawater/freshwater/soil/sediment samples for the presence of at least 10 different heavy metals.</p>
<p>SO2: Obtain quantitative, qualitative and distributional data regarding plastic pollution in the near-shore-open ocean terrestrial environment (the littoral zone) of the Arctic (remote sources/anthropogenic) and impacts/exchange. SO2 will address EO1 "Advanced scientific understanding of the impacts of pollution [...]" and EO5 "Assessment and monitoring tools developed [...]".</p>	
<p>R4. Determination of temporal and spatial dynamics of marine litter accumulation rates.</p> <p>R5. Estimation of the proportion of fishing-related plastic waste in the overall amount of stranded marine litter.</p> <p>R6. Enhancement in the number and performance of the automated marine litter identification with the presence of ground based labelled dataset and involving Citizen Scientists.</p> <p>R7. Quantification of microplastic concentration across the European Arctic Ocean.</p>	<p>1. Marine litter data collected from 20 km of continuous coastline in southern Spitsbergen over 2 years.</p> <p>2. Labelled marine litter dataset (for selected beach sections in 3 case study sites).</p> <p>3. 1 machine learning model trained to identify and categorise marine litter.</p> <p>4. # of Citizen Scientists (>20) trained in litter categorization and labelling.</p> <p>5. # of Citizen Scientists (>20) reporting macrolitter 6.# of microplastic particles per volume unit.</p>
<p>SO3: Determine the impact of the plastisphere antibiotic resistome (i.e., microbial diversity, genetic potential, and functional expression) and the role emergent pollutants (e.g., microplastics) play as a vector contributing to the spreading of antibiotic resistance across the European Arctic Gateway. SO3 will address EO1 "Advanced scientific</p>	

understanding of the impacts of pollution [...]”and EO2 “Advanced understanding of the main ecological, socio-economic and health [...]”.	
R8. Taxonomic information of the plastisphere microbial community, with a focus on antibiotic resistant bacteria (ARB). R9. Mechanistic understanding of the Arctic plastisphere antibiotic resistome and antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) with relevance for ecosystem and human health. R10. Novel insights into the role of microplastics and Atlantification (i.e., an inflow of warmer and saltier water into the Arctic Ocean) on the spreading of antibiotic resistance across the European Arctic Gateway.	1. # of the most abundant antibiotic resistant bacteria (ARB) (> 10) in the Arctic Ocean associated with microplastics. 2. # of the most active ARGs (> 10) of concern for human health in the European Arctic Ocean. 3.# of plastic-associated ARB and ARGs across the Arctic Ocean linked to ongoing Atlantification.
SO4: Determine the sensitivity of the marine microbial food web and of the associated trace gas production and consumption to pollution in combination with chronic climate-induced stressors: effects of pollution, including but not limited to ship traffic, on ecosystem health (i.e., microbial ecosystem dynamics and the cycling of climate active biogenic trace gases). SO4 will address EO1 “Advanced scientific understanding of the impacts of pollution [...]”and EO2 “Advanced understanding of the main ecological, socio-economic and health [...]”.	
R11. Identification of relevant pollutant sources influencing microbes and their by-products (from the range investigated, i.e., plastics, ship emissions, freshwater-runoff/melt and wastewater). R12. Quantification of the individual and synergistic impact of different pollution types, in combination with Climate Change scenarios (in particular with regard to temperature and pH), on the microbial community and element cycling. R13. Quantification of the impact of different pollution types on biogenic climate-active trace gases.	1.Growing database of relevant pollutant sources over the course of the project. 2. Identification of representative range of model solutions of microbial food web of unperturbed plankton ecosystem. 3. Temporarily and regionally distinguished percentage change in microbial activity and plankton community structure for individual and combined types, intensity and frequency of pollution, compared to baseline prior knowledge (unperturbed system). 4.Comparison of change in biogenic trace gas results over repetitive incubation experiments.
SO5: Determine the synergistic impacts of Climate Changes and human-induced pollution on human health. SO5 will address EO2 “Advanced understanding of the main ecological, socio-economic and health [...]”.	
R14. Analysis of the sanitary quality of the food chain by characterising chemical contamination using an exposomics approach. R15. Evaluation of toxicological impact of micro- and nano-plastics and other contaminants (PFAS) on human gut and gut/liver homeostasis in vitro.	1. Types and # of emerging chemical hazards (e.g., PFAS, halogenated (emerging) POPs) in sentinel species (e.g. mussels, fish, seal, plants) and sediments. 2. Types and # of toxicity endpoints affected after acute or repeated exposure in human intestinal/hepatic cell models.
SO6: Understand locally observed and perceived changes, impacts, risks, and vulnerabilities on ecosystem health, food security and safety, human health and well-being, and consequently design and pilot a user-centric	

environmental monitoring system to adapt to Climate Change and to mitigate pollution health risks. SO6 will address EO3 "Resilience and adaptation strategies [...]", EO4 "Contribute to making the case [...]", and EO5 "Assessment and monitoring tools developed [...]".	
R16. Identification of locally observed and perceived changes in traditional food species, beach/landscape dynamics, meteorological conditions, cryosphere, water quality, litter distribution, and resulting impacts, risks and vulnerabilities for health and well-being. R17. Community scenarios of change and adaptation and mitigation strategies to increase community and ecosystem resilience. R18. Pillars for a community-based environmental monitoring regarding Climate Change and human induced pollution.	1. # of reported changes (>10) in landscape, food resources, by local residents in Kalaallit Nunaat (Greenland) and Iceland case study sites. 2. # of climate-related indicators relevant for communities, based on observational data in case study sites. 3. # of reported perceived health and well-being impacts, risks and vulnerabilities by local residents (>10) in Greenland and Iceland. 4. # of vulnerable marine, coastal and terrestrial areas as observed by the communities in Greenland and Iceland. 5. # of interviews (>15) and # of workshops (>4) conducted in Iceland and Greenland. 6. # of community scenarios (>4). 7. # of culture-science land and marine camps (>2) with youth, elders, women, fishers, hunters and scientists.
SO7: Understand opportunities and shortcomings within multi-level governance approaches for local case studies, and consequently conceptualise complementary co-management/governance pollution-control approaches. SO7 will address EO3 "Resilience and adaptation strategies [...]", EO4 "Contribute to making the case [...]", and EO6 "Contribute to the implementation [...]".	
R19. Systematic governance mapping and analysis of formal and informal institutions and involved crucial actors regarding pollution-control (relevant for three case studies). R20. Analysis of synergies and incompatibilities of multilevel governance and local mitigation/adaptation concerns. R21. Elaboration of policy recommendations on major challenges of pollution governance in the Arctic.	1. # database of existing Arctic pollution governance approaches and structures. 2. # of best practice management examples identified in the project regarding pollution control and Climate Change adaptation. 3. # of policy reports (n=4) synthesising novel governance approaches for pollution control in the Arctic in the context of accelerating Climate Change.
SO8: Deepen the understanding of the gendered impacts of current pollution sources on Arctic communities. SO8 will address EO3 "Resilience and adaptation strategies [...]" and EO6 "Contribute to the implementation [...]".	
R22. Advanced understanding of the gender-dimension of socio-economic and health-associated risks and challenges of Arctic pollution, following a One Health approach. R23. Gender-based analysis identifying gaps and opportunities for integrating a gender-dimension	1. # of identified and recommended gender-related legal response measures and customary law to marine pollution. 2. # of key learnings on integrating a gender-dimension into trans interdisciplinary research on Arctic pollution.

of pollution into regional and global governance approaches to achieve One Health objectives.	
SO9: Co-develop tools for project evaluation in research collaborations across knowledge systems. SO9 will address EO3 "Resilience and adaptation strategies [...]" and EO6 "Contribute to the implementation [...]".	
R24. Advanced understanding of ethics and engagement protocols. R25. Ethics evaluation framework for co-creative research, including culturally appropriate evaluation tools.	1. Ethics evaluation framework for co-creative research 2. # of tools/methods for co-creative research and evaluation, esp. in collaboration across knowledge systems.